

Instructional Leadership Practices in School: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The importance of instructional leadership practice at school attracts the researcher to conduct a research. This article is used to analyze how the instructional leadership practices in schools. The review begins with internet that is google scholar searching for articles of instructional leadership as the keywords. There are several literature reviews of instructional leadership practices especially. Based on the literature reviews of various countries in Asia, we found that strong instructional leadership practices can build the teachers works by strengthening the system of organizational belief. These factors also can encourage students learning.

KEYWORDS: Instructional, Literature review, Leadership, Practice, School

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrial revolution 4.0 makes the era change so fast that educational system should transform to ensure a nation of giving the best education for the next generation. Along with these developments, almost all nations in the world is making improvement and re-evaluating the educational system in their country. Therefore the emphasize of the school leader quality is one of the key changes to mobilize educational transformation (Blase & Blase, 1999)

Education is one of the components which conduct a strategic way of for national development. Together with global life development, the excellence of a nation no longer relies only on natural resources. Nowadays, human resources act as important elements in an organization. Human resources are people that work in an organization called as personal, labor, and employees (Sunyoto, 2015). Human resources are defined as policies, practices, and systems that affect employee behaviors, attitude and performance (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, & Wright, 2010)

The humans' resources referred not only to the leaders but also the workers or employees. Stated in the job description, the leader becomes the main key to the progress of an organization, since the leader is a determinant, a manager, a controller for directing the goals of the organizations. In directing his employee, a leader must have self excellence over the people he leads. Therefore, an organization / institution need a leader with a leadership spirit that is able to manage all components in an institution he leads.

Leadership in an institution especially in the school is very important and significant in determining the effectiveness of the educational process. Related to this, it has been known that several studies have examined the importance of instructional leadership in managing the changes in the world of education (Goddard, Goddard, Sook Kim, & Miller, 2015; Le Fevre & Robinson, 2015; Ng, Nguyen, Wong, & Choy, 2015; Usman, 2015)

The 21st century school is considered leadership as an instructional leader (Rigby, 2014). The headmaster's instructional leadership places teachers as the main component that needs to be developed by building and encouraging the emergence of teacher's professionalism, innovative, creativity in the learning process (Hidayat, Herawan, & Prihatin, 2016; Southworth, 2002)

Instructional leadership is an instruction in the teaching-learning process and teachers have done their job concentrating on pedagogy, not on administration and delegation with others, focusing on student learning and providing practical form of school vision (Philip Hallinger, 2003; Phillip Hallinger & Lee, 2014; Niqab, Sharma, Wei, & Maulod, 2014)

Instructional leadership related positively to teacher's citizenship behaviors. Mehmet Sisman in his research explained that through various support for the teacher as the problem solving effectively makes teacher more succeed and productive. Besides, teacher who focused on their works is able to work also with their partner in school. It emphasizes how important headmasters' role in organizing the teacher and giving professional supports for the effective learning activity and students' maximum learning outcomes. Headmaster instructional leadership put the teacher as the main component that need full attention and developed. As leadership concepts which focused on learning process and teachers' behavior in serving the students, therefore the headmaster as an

instructional leadership focused on developing education quality and influencing extra role of teacher's behaviors. Teacher doing his work enthusiastically and giving all his ability in doing his work. Based on the description, it is necessary to know deeper about "How Instructional Leadership practice at School in Asia".

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. Principal's Leadership

The term leadership comes from the English word "leader" which means leader or to lead. Many definitions of leadership are put forward by the experts according to their perspective points of view, which depends on the perspective used. Leadership can be defined based on its application of certain division in an organization. The followings are some of the definitions of leadership which is put forward by the experts (Sobahi)

Leadership according to Heifetz is a social activity (Aravena, 2019) Wahjosumijo argues that leadership is an important force in management, therefore the ability to lead effectively is the key to become an effective manager. Sarros and Butchatsky: "Leadership is defined as the purposeful behavior of influencing others to contribute to a commonly agree goal for the benefits of individual as well as the organization or common good".

According to this definition, leadership can be defined as a behavior with a specific purpose to influence the activities of a group member to achieve common goals that is provide individual and organizational benefits (Herawan, 2016). Kouzes and Posner argue that leadership is the people who contribute a creation to realizing something extraordinary (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

According to (Yukl, 2010), some definitions that are considered to be the representative for a quarter century are as follows:

1. Leadership is the behavior of an individual who leads the activities of a group to achieve the goals together (shared goals).
2. Leadership is interpersonal influence that is exercised in a certain situation, and directed through the communication process towards achieving one or several specific goals.
3. Leadership is the initial formation and maintenance of structure in expectations and interactions.
4. Leadership is increasing influence gradually, all over mechanical adherence to the routine directives of the organization.
5. Leadership is the process of influencing the activities of a group organized towards achieving goals.

Leadership is a process of giving meaning (meaningful direction) to collective efforts, which resulted in a willingness to make effort to achieve goals.

7. Leaders are those who consistently make an effective contribution to the social order, who are expected and perceived to do so.

According to Hanson, the term of leadership can be understood as a concept which implies that there is a process of power that comes from a figure leader to influence others either individually or in groups of an organization (Masaong & Tilomi, 2011). There are several things that need to be considered in explaining about leader and leadership, including:

1. Power and authority, the ability to act for a leader to move his employee to follow his will in achieving predetermined goals;
2. Authority, the various advantages possessed by a leader, so that it distinguishes him from the one he leads, with these advantages other people will obey and are willing to carry out activities that he wants;
3. Ability, overall power, both in the form of social skills and technical skills that exceed others (Sopan Adrianto, 2019)

In organizations, leaders are divided into three main levels:

1. Top manager: whose task is implementing the administration in preparing plans, policies and reports consisting of the board of directors;
2. Middle Manager: the executives implementing organizational plans and policies which consisting the heads of divisions;
3. Low Manager: the executives in the field consisting the heads of units, the supervisors (Ardana, Mujiati, & Utama, 2012) .

In the Minister of National Education Regulation (Permendiknas) no 28 of 2010 explained about the assignment of teachers as headmasters / madrasas. Principals / madrasas are teachers who are given additional duties to lead an education unit. There are some indicators that principals should acquire to manage a school effectively: a) have a strong vision for the future of their schools; b) have high expectations; c) ensure teaching learning process to run effectively; d) time management and minimize conflicts; e) make use of existing learning resources; f) utilize the information to a direct learning planning; g) carry out continuous evaluation and improvement (Mardalena, 2019).

According to (Chapman, 1975), there are several leadership variables: 1) how to communicate, each leader must be able to provide clear information and communicate well and smoothly; 2) giving motivation, having the ability to provide encouragement and motivate financially or non-financially, that in terms of appreciation or recognition. It is a very high meaning gift to employees or workers; 3) the ability to lead, this can be seen in his leadership style, whether he has an autocratic, participatory or free of control leadership style; 4) decision maker, a leader must be able to make decisions based on facts and applicable regulations in the company and the decisions taken are able to motivate employees to work better and to increase work productivity; and 5) positive power, a leader in running an organization or company, although with different leadership styles, must provide a sense of secure for the employees.

The importance of the role of leadership in an organization has become a focus that attracts the attention of researchers in the field of organizational behavior, stating the quality of leaders is often considered the most important factor determining the success or failure of an organization (Bass & Avolio, 1990)

Based on the opinion of these experts, leadership can be interpreted as a trait or ability that a leader must possess in influencing his worker to achieve a goal. The principal is the person who has the highest power in the school, therefore the principal is responsible for all school activities and plays an important role in improving the quality of education (Brooks & Brooks, 2019; Eisenschmidt, Kuusisto, Poom-Valickis, & Tirri, 2019; Truong, Hallinger, & Sanga, 2017). Leadership is a process of influencing other people to behave in accordance with the wishes of the leader (Azizah, Latief, & Tumanggung, 2018).

The leadership of the principal involves trying to elevate people's views beyond self-interest towards joint efforts, for common goals (Winardi, Nurkolis, & Yuliejantiningasih, 2017). The function of leadership is to build organizational conditions that foster high quality teaching and the result is in the improvements of learning outcomes (Leithwood, Harris, & Hopkins, 2008). The potential students can be influenced by the leadership of the principal (Urlick, 2016). The principal plays a role as a central force that becomes the driving force for school life (Setiyati, 2014).

People have different ability to lead, meaning that not every person or leader is able to lead. This can be seen in their leadership style, whether they have an autocratic, participatory or free of control leadership style. Each of them has advantages and disadvantages. If the leader is an autocratic leadership style, then the control of decision making will be entirely in the hands of the leader. In the participatory leadership style, the control of decision making includes the employees. While in the leadership free of control style, the decision making is with the employees but it is still beyond full leadership control (Chapman, 1975).

Three types of headmaster profile types were identified: "people-thinking profiles", "administratively minded profiles" and "moderate thinking profiles" (Dou, Devos, & Valcke, 2017). According to Hallinger, instructional leaders are seen as the main source of knowledge for education program development (Bass & Avolio, 1990). Principals have the greatest access to the district leaders, parents, community members, school staff and students (Philip Hallinger, Walker, Nguyen, Truong, & Nguyen, 2017). One of the principal ways' to establish the instructional leadership is by using an evaluation system to influence learning, develop teacher classroom instruction, and improve student achievement (McNeill, Lowenhaupt, & Katsh-Singer, 2018). The task of the principal, as a school leader, is a complex and diverse endeavor. Recent investigations have found that the principals who emphasize instructional leadership behaviors have a stronger positive impact on student achievement than the principals who emphasize other styles (Boyce & Bowers, 2018).

B. Instructional Leadership

This type of leadership is often referred to leadership behavior or leadership style. According to Machali and Kurniadin, leadership style is behavior and strategy, which is a combination of philosophies, skills, traits, and behaviors that are applied by a leader to influence the performance of his followers (Kurniadin, Machali, & Sandra, 2013). Sutikno said the leadership style or leadership behaviors are often called the Leadership Type (Sutikno, 2014). According to Miftah Toha, leadership style is a behavior norm that is used by a person when that person tries to influence the behavior of others (Toha, 2013).

There are two general concepts of instructional leadership, narrow and broad. The narrow concept defines instructional leadership as actions that are directly related to teaching and learning process, such as conducting classroom observations. This is the conceptualization of instructional leadership used in the 1980s and usually applied in the context of small elementary schools or schools that are still in the process of development which are mostly located in the countryside. A broad view of instructional leadership includes all leadership activities that indirectly affect student learning such as school culture and time scheduling procedures. This might be considered an aspect of leadership that impacts the quality of the curriculum and instruction delivered by

students. This conceptualization recognizes the principal as an instructional leader has a positive impact on student learning but this influence is mediated.

A comprehensive instructional leadership model was developed by Hallinger and Murphy. This dominant model proposes three broad dimensions of instructional leadership constructs: defining school missions, managing national program instructions and promoting a positive school learning climate. These dimensions are further described into 10 instructional leadership functions as follows: (1) frame school goals, (2) communicate school goals, (3) coordinate the curriculum, (4) oversee and evaluate instruction, (5) monitor student progress, (6) protect teaching time, (7) provide incentives for teachers, (8) provide incentives for learning, (9) promote professional development and (10) maintain high visibility (Ng et al., 2015).

School principals are increasingly demanded to be able to lead the changes in a better direction and improve the quality of education. Principal's leadership appears not only in the leadership style but also in the practiced instructional leader-ship aspect. Instructional leadership is leadership at schools or colleges that emphasizes improving the quality of teaching and learning. This leadership is not attached only to the principal because the success of education is achieved jointly by a number of people in various roles in the school. Principals should apply the instructional leadership to improve the school quality by establishing high expectations for all children, maintaining the school environment, implementing periodic evaluations, and focusing on academic activities. Instructional leaders should advance and develop their school as a professional learning organization or community to achieve school learning goals for their students. Therefore, the principal carries out many roles, those are as managers, regulators, teaching leaders and curriculum leaders (Nandi Wardhana, 2016)

Transactional leadership according to Metcalfe, transactional leaders must have clear information about what their employees need and want. He must provide constructive feedback to maintain their employees in their duties. In transactional relationships, the leader promises and rewards his employees who perform well, threatens and disciplines his underperforming employee (Alimo-Metcalfe, 1995).

Bernard M. Bass argues that transactional leadership is leadership where leaders determine what employees must do so that they can achieve their own or organizational goals and help employees gain confidence in doing these tasks (Bass & Avolio, 1990).

Instructional leadership refers to the process and approach undertaken by the school principals to exert influence on the aspects related to schooling and learning. There are five dimensions of instructor's instructional leadership; design and articulate learning objectives, design learning strategies, monitor the learning process, support and maximize the potential of teachers, and create instructional learning environments.

School instructional leadership indicators include; apply knowledge, skills and important concepts in learning; facilitate collaboration (team); designing resource allocation and the use of strategies; guiding teachers in teaching and supervising learning in the classroom (Sidupa, 2018)

Kudisch, argues that transactional leadership can be described as:

1. Exchange something valuable for others between the leader and his employee.
2. Interventions carried out as an organizational process to control and correct the errors.
3. The reaction to not achieving predetermined standards (Kudisch, 2010).

Instructional leadership theory originally from the studies conducted at schools in the United States in the 1980s, which offers substantial and varied empirical evidence that instructional leadership has an indirect but significant effect on student achievement. The Principal Management Instructional Rating Scale developed by Hallinger and Murphy is one of the most enduring instructional leadership models. The author creates an instructional leadership model with three dimensions: defining mission schools, managing teaching programs and developing a learning climate in schools (Qian, Walker, & Li, 2017).

Instructional leadership is a leadership that influences self-efficacy in teaching, improves classroom learning through teachers and positively affects the knowledge / understanding, teaching implementation (Afrina, Rohiat, & Zakaria, 2018). The way of principal's instructional leadership in carrying out their duties and responsibilities greatly affects teacher performance, because successful leaders are the leaders who are able to manage and empower the resources in his educational institution (Afrina, 2019; Ithnin & Abdullah, 2018)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This literature review focuses on instructional leadership practices at school.

A. Literature Search Process.

The review process begins with a search engine, Google scholar, to search for articles entitled "instructional leadership". Searches are limited to articles by 2015-2019 publication years. After being identified, there were 150 articles related to this theme. The criteria of the articles in this study are:

1. Results of qualitative research on instructional leadership practices at school
2. Asian research (conducted in Asian's country)
3. The article must be written in English
4. Dissertations and thesis are excluded

The steps in the Literature Review of Leadership Instruction include:

Step 1: Formulate the Problem

- Choose a topic that fits to the issue and interest.
- The problem must be written completely and accurately.

Step 2: Look for the Literature

- Look for relevant literature.
- Get an overview of the research topic.
- Research sources are very helpful if it is supported by knowledge of the topic being studied.
- These sources provide an overview / summary of the previous research.

Step 3: Evaluate the Data

- Look at any contribution to the topic discussed,
- Search and find the right data source as needed to support the research,
- Data can be in the form of qualitative data, quantitative data or a combination of both qualitative and quantitative.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. Instructional Leadership Practices in School

Author and Publication Year	Title	Country	Methods	Sample	Results
Felipe Aravena, 2017	Destructive Leadership Behavior: An Exploratory Study In Chile	Chile	Qualitative	--	The leader has an influence on the teacher's perception of the leadership process.
Joseph Blasé and Jo Blasé, 2014	Principals' Instructional Leadership And Teacher's Development: Teachers' Perspectives	United States	Qualitative	Male teachers 251, Female teachers = 558 from village (n = 275), outskirts (n = 291), and school location in urban areas (n = 243).	In terms of the benefits of the interaction of the principal who implements instructional leadership with the teacher, can provide effective encouragement in teaching, research, and exploration. With instructional leadership style, teachers will have more attention, so teachers become more explorative in choosing learning methods and models.

Jared Boyce and Alex J. Bowers, 2017	Toward An Evolving Conceptualization Of Instructional Leadership As Leadership For Learning	United States	Qualitative	52 principals	First, we have identified the four instructional leadership factors most discussed in 109 quantitative studies: leadership and principal's effect, autonomy and teacher's impact, adult development, and school climate. Second, we have identified three factors that are most frequently researched in relation to these themes: teacher satisfaction, teacher commitment, and teacher retention. Third, we have described the correlation between instructional factors and assessed the evidence related to each of these correlations. Fourth, we have integrated those correlations into a single model that maps how those factors and correlations fit together
Melanie C. Brooks and Jeffrey S. Brooks, 2018	Culturally (Ir) Relevant School Leadership: Ethno-Religious Conflict And School Administratin In The Philippines	Australia	Qualitative		The principal in northern Mindanao is a leader that is not culturally relevant. They apply the status quo to the marginalization of students from various backgrounds. As a result, some students receive the opportunity to get a quality education while others do not.
Diya Dou, Geert Devos and Martin Valcke, 2016	The Relationships Between School Autonomy Gap, Principal Leadership Teachers' Job Satisfaction Organization Commitment	China	Qualitative	528 teachers and 59 principals.	The significance of the impact of instructional and transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction and organizational commitment, mediated by school welfare and teacher self-efficacy.
KatrinPoom-Valickis and KirsiTirri, 2019	Leadership: Exemplary Principals From Estonia And Finland	Firlandia	Quantitative		Building schools for future generations.
Roger Goddard, Yvonne Goddard,	A Theoretical And Empirical Analysis	United States	Quantitative	93 elementary	The strong instructional leadership can create a good

and Eun Sook Kim, 2015	Of The Roles Of Instructional Leadership, Teacher Collaboration, And Collective Efficacy Belief S In Support Of Student Learning			schools	system that can facilitate the work of teachers that strengthen trust in organization, and, together, these factors will increase student achievement.
Phillip Hallinger And Moosung Lee, 2014	Mapping Instructional Leadership In Thailand: Has Education Reform Impacted Principal Practice	Thailand	Qualitative		Expectations of a new system for principals to act as instructional leaders, Thailand's dominant principal orientation has remained unchanged
Angela Urick, 2015	Examining Us Principal Perception Of Multiple Leadership Styles Used To Practice Shared Instructional Leadership	United States	Quantitative	8.524 principals	Principals must pay equal attention to the resources, safety and facilities because the principal's work emphasizes the basic needs of the school.
Thang Dinh Truong, Philip Hallinger And Kabini Sanga, 2016	Confucian Values And School Leadership In Vietnam: Exploring The Influence Of Culture On Principal Decision Making	Vietnam	Qualitative		The powerful influence of power and collectivism on the decision making of principals in Vietnam.
Jessica G. Rigby, 2014	Three Logics Of Instructional Leadership	United States	Content Analysis Method		Three conceptions of instructional leadership in institutions are: entrepreneurial logic, entrepreneurship, and social justice.
Haiyan Qian Allan Walker Xiaojun Li, 2017	The West Wind Vs The East Wind: Instructional Leadership Model In China	China	Qualitative		Leadership practices need to be understood in relation to different historical, cultural, and social contexts.

Foo Seong David Ng, Thanh Dong Nguyen, KoonSiak Benjamin Wong, and KimWeng William Choy, 2015	Instructional Leadership Practices In Singapore	Singapore	Qualitative		The principal gives an influence on learning and the quality of teaching by creating a comfortable school climate. Besides, the subjects in secondary school are more specialized than subjects in primary school. This brings deeper compartments in the secondary school context.
Kenneth Leithwooda, Alma Harrisband David Hopkins, 2019	Seven Strong Claims About Successful School Leadership Revisited	London	Qualitative	-	Research on school leadership has produced several strong claims. The main reason for holding this research is the lack of programmed research; lack of evidence collected from small and large-scale studies, failure to use various research designs, and failure to provide sufficient quantities of evidence, and sufficient quality to be a strong guide for policy and practice.
Deidre M. Le Fevre1 and Viviane M. J. Robinson, 2014	The Interpersonal Challenges Of Instructional Leadership: Principals' Effectiveness In Conversations About Performance Issues	Zaeland	Quantitative	30 principals	The principal shows consistently low to moderate skill levels (based on interview results). Principals are usually more skilled in advocating for their own positions than in-depth investigating and checking their understanding of the views of parents or teachers.
Philip Hallinger, Allan Walker, Dao Thi Hong Nguyen, 2016 Thang Truong, Thi Thinh Nguyen, 2016	Perspectives On Principal Instructional Leadership In Vietnam: A Preliminary Model	Vietnam	Qualitative	27 principals	This research proved that the initial instructional leadership model in Vietnam has similarities with the instructional leadership model in the west, by including dimensions that focus on setting direction, managing curriculum and instruction and developing a learning climate in schools.

Eve Eisenschmidt, Elina Kuusisto	Virtues That Create Purpose For Ethical	Finland	Qualitative		Principals must use wisdom and knowledge in creating long-term policies for their schools.
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This article discussed instructional leadership practices of various schools at various countries in Asia. Most articles focused on how instructional leadership practices at schools. Based on the reviewed articles, there are various ways of collecting the data related to instructional leadership at schools; the most commonly used are interviews and observation.

Research on instructional leadership practices at various schools in Asia has been carried out in various countries. Table 1 showed that the research on this theme has been carried out at various levels of education, including universities (higher education). Most research showed that strong instructional leadership can create structures to facilitate the work of teachers by strengthening belief systems in organizations, to increase students' achievements. But in the research conducted by Diya Dou, Geert Devos and Martin Valcke, the significance influence's of instructional and transformational leadership on teacher's job satisfaction and organizational commitment, coupled with the indirect could impact the school climate and teacher's self-efficacy (Dou et al., 2017), this showed that in practicing instructional leadership on teacher job satisfaction mediated by the indirect could impact the school climate and teacher self-efficacy.

The principal must involve the teachers in developing and implementing learning objectives. The school principal must refer to the curriculum that is set by the government. Principals in implementing instructional leadership must work together with teachers to improve learning programs in class according to student needs. The instructional leadership can communicate the vision and mission of the school to the teachers and staff. The principal promotes and implements the contents of the school's vision well. The principal must be able to develop the habits of sharing opinions in determining the vision and mission of the school, and the principal must maintain the vision and mission of the school in order to remain well implemented, because the concept of instructional leadership is to focus on teaching and learning activities and on teacher's behaviour in serving students. Supported by Roger Goddard, Yvonne Goddard, Eun Sook Kim, who stated that strong instructional leadership, can create structures to facilitate teacher work by strengthening organizational belief systems and encouraging factors to improve the quality of education. (Goddard et al., 2015).

General conclusions from studies on instructional leadership practices at school from various countries in Asia showed that the principal's leadership style is very important for an organization, included educational institutions. It has a positive and negative impacts. It influences academic achievement in education. Just like other studies, this review also has the limitations. First, the articles reviewed were only articles written in English, so there were still many studies from various countries that were not reviewed due to language limitations. Second, dissertations and thesis were not discussed in this article because they can cause publication bias. Third, the scope of the article reviewed was still very limited, in this paper the scope was limited for the research conducted at several Asian countries and some countries with good quality education in the world. And the last, there is no single measure that can compare across studies.

5. CONCLUSION

Principal's leadership is very important for developing the school, because the leaders can create positive changes in education by encouraging staff to take initiative and changes. The results of this literature review indicate that the principal's leadership style is very important for an organization, including educational institutions, and has positive and negative impacts. It influences academic achievements in education. Instructional leadership is a leadership model that influences teacher's self- efficacy. Through this leadership style, principal will easily motivate teachers to improve classroom learning, which positively influences their knowledge/understanding, teaching quality, competencies and self-efficacy individually and collectively.

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